

Title

Mind-Brain: A Hypothesis of One Pathogenetic Process

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Abstract

In the history of psychiatry, a central and always contentious issue is the origin of mental illness, specifically how the mind-brain system could become diseased, leading to madness. This paper will outline one of the possible pathogenic hypotheses where the "overfunctioning" of the mind is linked to an inflammatory process, which in turn leads to cortical dysregulation. This "overfunctioning" has been described numerous times in the literature with different perspectives and terms such as Wahnstimmung, obsessions, ruminations, and rumination, extensively discussed not only by Jaspers and Freud but also in Cognitive Behavioral Therapy and even in the literature itself. More recent studies on the role of the glutamatergic system are highlighting how its dysregulation is an early event and central to the pathogenesis in both neurology and psychiatry, likely affecting the entire spectrum of neuroses, psychoses, mood disorders, and neurodegenerative processes.

Keywords: inflammatory; psychiatry; rumination; microglia; astrocyte; psychosis; NMDA; glutamatergic; mitochondrial; metabolism

Abbreviations

ATP: adenosine triphosphate

CL: cardiolipin

Cytc: cytochrome c

asseHPA: asse Ipotalamo-Ipofisi-Surrene

mtDNA: mitochondrial DNA

mtDAMP: mitochondrial damage-associated molecular pattern

ROS: reactive oxygen species

TFAM: mitochondrial transcription factor A

Introduction

In the history of psychiatry, a central and continuously contentious issue has been the origin of mental illness, specifically how the mind-brain system could become diseased, leading to psychosis. The debate between organic and psychological origins persists today, although contemporary therapeutic approaches often involve both pharmacological and psychotherapeutic interventions, suggesting involvement of both domains and rendering the Mind-Brain dualism more of an academic exercise. This paper attempts to outline a pathogenesis hypothesis where hyperfunctioning of the mind is correlated with an inflammatory process, which in turn leads to cortical dysregulation—a hypothesis that current scientific literature considers one of the pathogenetic theories for psychoses and mood disorders. In philosophy (e.g., Kierkegaard S, *The Concept of anxiety - Begrebet Angest*), literature (e.g., Kafka F, *The Metamorphosis - Die Verwandlung*, 1915), and various schools of psychotherapy (e.g., Psychoanalysis and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy), descriptions of psychic suffering often focus on the uncontrollable repetitiveness of thought, with resulting "difficulty in maintaining attention" and concentration, as central to the process. These patterns have been described as Obsessions, Worries primarily concerning the unpredictable unknown, Ruminations oriented towards the past in association with

self-deficiencies, or more generally as delusional states characterized by rigid constructs. These elements are documented in various psychopathological frameworks (e.g., Freud S in “The Rat Man” 1909, Totem and Taboo 1913, [1] Papageorgiou and Wells, 2004; [2] Watkins, Moulds, and McIntosh, 2005; Jaspers K 1913; DSM-5) and are associated with accelerated, perseverative, and redundant thinking, leading to the subjective sensation that something indecipherable is about to occur (“Wahnstimmung” Jaspers, 1959). Today, we understand that hyperactivity, which is a common biological effort across all psychopathological conditions albeit with different psychic contents, correlates with an inflammatory process and cortical dysregulation, no longer managed by GABA neurons ([3] Sthal SM 2021, 6th chapter).

This brief paper aims to identify, through the repetitiveness of psychic processes, the cause of the inflammatory process, which would arise due to hyperfunctioning (similar to other tissues such as the pancreas, muscles, etc.) of the Corticocortical pathway mediated by GABAergic neurons (with involvement of Glutamatergic receptors and GABAergic transmission).

Development

In the past, the most widely accepted theory for schizophrenia was the dopaminergic hypothesis. However, this hypothesis has struggled to explain the origin of the hyperactivity in the mesolimbic pathway, the hypoactivity in the mesocortical pathway, and how its management fails to halt cognitive decline. Cognitive decline is also evident in mood disorders, where increased activation of brain regions involved in cognitive control has been observed. Specifically, intervention in glutamatergic and GABAergic systems has been shown to counteract synaptic loss that precedes neuronal loss ([3] Stahl SM 2021, 6th chapter).

Recent studies on the role of the glutamatergic system are highlighting its central role in the pathogenesis of psychiatric disorders (as well as in neurology), likely affecting the entire spectrum of psychoses, including mood disorders and neuroses. Specifically, early stages of the disease have shown prefrontal hyperactivity due to NMDA receptor hypofunction on GABAergic interneurons. In schizophrenia, there is a reduction in GABAergic interneuron activity, leading to excessive activation of cortical glutamatergic projections in the Ventral Tegmental Area (VTA), which in turn increases dopamine release from mesostriatal projections and enhances mesolimbic activity or reduces mesocortical activity due to mediation by other GABAergic interneurons in the limbic area ([4] Paz RD et al. 2008; [3] Stahl SM 2021, 4th chapter; [5] Meixensberger S et al. 2020).

In depression, beyond the neurotransmitter deficit hypothesis, which was later integrated by findings of post-receptor upregulation, there is now the hypothesis of involvement of the Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (HPA) axis of multifactorial origin. This hypothesis emphasizes neurons in the hippocampus and amygdala that normally suppress the HPA axis, but under stress conditions, their atrophy would lead to loss of inhibitory input to the hypothalamus (evidenced by increased glucocorticoids, which are potentially neurotoxic, and resistance to their negative feedback on the HPA axis). In both structures, the neurons responsible for negative feedback are GABAergic interneurons. International literature now recognizes the presence and involvement of neuroinflammation, mediated by microglia, which interferes with the HPA axis, leading to synaptic loss and neuronal death. Additionally, depressed patients exhibit increased activation in brain regions involved in cognitive control, such as the prefrontal cortex and the anterior cingulate cortex, which are also under negative feedback control by GABAergic interneurons, with astrocytes playing a critical role in modulating transmission by providing ATP to neurons and participating in neurotransmission. Cognitive dysfunction in depression is present and correlates with the number of past episodes ([3] Stahl SM 2021, 6th chapter).

Therefore, a growing focus in recent research on psychiatric and neurological pathogenesis is the role of inflammation, confirmed by elevated levels of inflammatory mediators in the vast majority of psychiatric conditions ([6] Brites D et al., 2015). Improvement in psychoses and/or depression with the concomitant administration of NSAIDs in depressed individuals, who also show resistance to monoamine reuptake inhibitors, tricyclics, ketamine, and ECT, with abnormal increases in

various pro-inflammatory activity markers ([7] Fond G et al. 2020; [8] Roman M, 2020) supports this. Although the CNS contains a variety of inflammatory cells, microglia and astrocytes appear to be the most involved. Microglia, analogous to peripheral immune macrophages, and astrocytes perform numerous functions, including maintaining ion concentrations inside and outside neurons and supporting the blood-brain barrier ([8] Roman M, 2020). Supporting evidence includes abnormal microglial activation and their increased number observed in depression and anxiety disorders ([9] Serafini et al., 2015). Inflammatory findings have also been noted in autopsy analyses of brain tissue in suicides ([10] Stockmeier CA et al. 2004; [11] Steiner et al., 2011; [12] Black C. 2015).

Regarding depression, microglial activation can alter monoamine metabolic pathways, which are crucial for regulating excitation and reward mechanisms. Specifically, these central inflammatory signals, via mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathways, increase the number and activity of presynaptic reuptake pumps, reducing monoamine availability (serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine) in the neuronal synapse. Additionally, these pro-inflammatory cytokines also activate the enzyme indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO), which metabolizes tryptophan into kynurenine, thereby reducing the availability of this primary serotonin precursor. Activated microglia then convert kynurenine into quinolinic acid. When quinolinic acid binds to the N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor, a glutamate receptor, it increases glutamate release, an excitatory amino acid neurotransmitter ([8] Roman M, 2020), thereby increasing the metabolic stress on the involved circuits and their controlling interneurons. The common and transdiagnostic relationship of inflammatory processes in psychoses (schizophrenia and bipolar disorder) is therefore considered from various perspectives ([13] Jauhar S et al. 2017; [14] Meier UC et al. 2020).

All these considerations understandably highlight the role of anti-inflammatory treatments ([15] Kohler-Forsberg O, 2020; [7] Fond O, 2020).

In the context of inflammatory pathogenesis, glial cells (primarily microglia and astrocytes), which are part of the local immune system, play a crucial role in glutamatergic and GABAergic transmission. Specifically, in addition to their role in ATP synthesis for neurons, glutamate synthesis from glutamine predominantly occurs in astrocytes. These cells also play a key role in glutamatergic transmission as co-transmitters at the NMDA receptor. This process is only possible if glycine (Gly) is present along with the glutamate secreted by neurons. In GABAergic transmission, astrocytes not only support ATP synthesis for neurons but also facilitate transmission through neurosteroids ([3] Stahl SM 2021, 6th and 7th chapters; [16] Hong J 2020).

An important concept to address is "aseptic inflammation," which refers to inflammation occurring without the presence of infectious agents like bacteria, viruses, or fungi, but due to physical trauma, chemical substances, toxins, mechanical stress, autoimmune diseases, or foreign bodies. Mitochondria are the centers of energetic metabolism, and in the context of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) metabolic disturbances, high energy demands can lead to structural and functional damage to mitochondria. While the exact pathogenesis of T2DM remains uncertain in every detail, recent years have clarified many aspects, such as the central role of mitochondrial damage and how excessive glucose exposure—along with the consequent hyperactivity of beta cells and oxygen availability—can either negatively affect or positively influence pathogenesis by impacting the production and regulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), thereby affecting mitochondrial function. T2DM is associated with oxidative-redox imbalances and resulting chronic inflammation. Damaged mitochondria or dead cells release molecules (mtDAMPs, including mtDNA, ATP, TFAM, CL, and Cytc) that induce inflammation and cellular damage. The molecular model associated with mitochondrial damage initiates and participates in inflammatory processes within and around cells ([17] Wang Y et al. 2024).

Oxidative inflammatory processes, similar to those in stressed pancreatic beta cells or other stressed functional cells, initially impact mitochondrial metabolism, reducing functional capacity and causing intoxication in eukaryotic cells more exposed to stress and with higher ATP demands. This

leads to activation of microglia (which, like resident immune cells, are involved in immune surveillance, phagocytosis of cellular debris, and pathogen elimination) and subsequent inflammatory response (through phagocytosis, cytokine release, and modulation of synaptic plasticity through interactions with neurons and other glial cells). The hypothesis proposed here is the involvement of astrocytes in the inflammatory process of mitochondria. Astrocytes are particularly exposed to increased ATP synthesis demands (since they synthesize ATP both for themselves and for neurons) and cortical hyperactivity (due to their role in glutamatergic and GABAergic transmission) in circuits responsible for controlling, via GABAergic interneurons, the same hyperactivity.

The brain's susceptibility to energy deficiency (due to hyperactivity) and the consequent increased vulnerability of the mitochondrial system is attributed to the brain's high oxygen consumption (about 20% of the body's consumption) despite representing only about 2% of a human's body weight. Not only neurodegenerative diseases and diabetes but also aging itself is now considered within a process centered around mitochondria, as proposed by Harman D in the "Mitochondrial Theory of Aging" decades ago. As mentioned earlier, mitochondria play a central role in many processes: energy synthesis, intracellular calcium buffering (regulating neuronal excitability), homeostasis, steroid synthesis (affecting cell growth and apoptosis), and inflammation and ROS synthesis. The resultant excess of free radical production secondary to mitochondrial distress is correlated with: compartmentalization damage due to lipid peroxidation, leading to cell death; protein damage with alterations in enzymatic functions and increased ROS production; and interactions with mitochondrial and nuclear DNA damage, which in turn affects mitochondrial function itself. The activation of the immune response following mitochondrial damage is well-documented and related to the integration of an alpha-proteobacterial phototroph approximately 2 billion years ago, whose damage now activates alarmins or "auto-molecules" (mtDAMPs) including various mitochondrial molecules such as its DNA, cardiolipin (CL) (present exclusively in the inner mitochondrial membrane), and other mitochondrial proteins as previously listed ([18] Bartman S et al. 2024; [19] Aguilar K et al. 2024).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the pathogenesis is hypothesized to arise from the overactivity of GABAergic interneurons, which are connected to intracortical glutamatergic pyramidal neurons, and are aimed at inhibiting hyperactivity (e.g., manifesting as rumination or worry symptoms). This process would subsequently involve glial cells in inflammation, leading to NMDA receptor hypo-function. As previously described, glial cells are responsible for both inflammation and transmission through glycine, and they also provide glutamine for glutamate synthesis. Alternatively, this can involve alterations in GABAergic synthesis, resulting in loss of control and hyperfunction of the mesolimbic pathways, dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, and anterior cingulate cortex during the early stages of these disorders.

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Hypothesis
origin disease
Mind-Brain

Rumination
Obsessions
Worry

Central Nervous System (CNS)
Fatigue
(in control areas, in cells with
high ATP synthesis activity)

Inflammation with Hypofunction
In the Glutamatergic neuron system – GABAergic interneuron system – Astrocytes
Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (DLPFC) and Anterior Cingulate Cortex (ACC).

Loss of control with acceletarion in:
Mesolimbic pathway
DLPFC
ACC

Prevalence of thought disorders (e.g. Schizophrenia)
Prevalence of mood disorders (e.g. Depression, Anxie,
Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder,
chronic pain and dysregulation of
motivation/reward processing)

- Legend:**
- ATP (Adenosine Triphosphate)
 - GABA (Gamma-Aminobutyric Acid)
 - Gly (Glycine)
 - Glu (Glutamate)
 - Gln (Glutamine)
 - Lac (Lactate)

